

LokNirikshan: A Blockchain-Inspired Election Transparency and Management System

Sachin Yadav, Khushi Johri, Manish Kumar, Ashish Kumar Jha, Arzu

LOVELY PROFESSIONAL UNIVERSITY PHAGWARA, PUNJAB

ABSTRACT

Elections play a very important role in any democratic country, but many existing systems still face several issues such as lack of transparency, slow processing, and chances of data manipulation. In many cases, people are not fully able to trust how the results are generated because the internal processes are not clearly visible to the public. Due to this, there is a strong need for a system that can improve trust and make election processes more open and secure.

In this paper, we present *LokNirikshan*, which is a blockchain-inspired election transparency and management system. Instead of depending completely on traditional or fully decentralized blockchain systems, this project takes useful ideas from blockchain such as cryptographic hashing, audit trails, and data verification, and applies them in a more practical and easier-to-use web-based system.

The system is designed to handle the complete election process from start to end. It includes voter registration, party management, election setup, voting process, result calculation, and public verification. One important feature of the system is the use of Merkle trees, which help in verifying that the data has not been changed after it is stored. This allows users or observers to check the correctness of results without needing to trust the system blindly.

We have developed LokNirikshan using React for the frontend, Node.js and Express for the backend, and MongoDB for storing data. The system supports different types of users such as voters, party representatives, party heads, and administrators, where each role has its own responsibilities and access. Along with this, features like anomaly detection and public verification portal are also included to improve reliability and transparency.

For testing, we have used a dataset of 500 simulated voters across multiple constituencies. The system was able to successfully perform all election stages and detect irregularities in most cases. Verification using Merkle proofs also worked correctly for all valid records.

Overall, LokNirikshan provides a more transparent and structured approach to managing elections. It may not be fully decentralized, but it still improves trust and accountability by making the process more open and verifiable.

KEYWORDS— Election transparency, electronic voting (e-voting), blockchain-inspired architecture, Merkle tree verification, cryptographic hashing, audit trail systems, role-based access control (RBAC), digital governance platforms, constituency-based election management, voter registration systems, anomaly detection in elections, data integrity verification, public result verification, distributed trust models, secure election systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Elections are one of the most important parts of any democratic system. They give people the power to choose their leaders and take part in governance. However, for elections to work properly, people must trust the system. If there is doubt about how votes are collected or counted, then even correct results can be questioned.

In many places, traditional voting systems are still used, such as paper ballots or basic electronic machines. While these methods work, they also come with several problems. Paper-based systems can be slow and difficult to manage,

especially in large countries where millions of people vote. On the other hand, electronic systems can be faster, but they are often not transparent enough. Most of the process happens inside the system, and common people cannot easily verify whether everything is done correctly.

Another major issue is centralization. In many current systems, the control is handled by a single authority or a limited number of entities. This creates a risk because if something goes wrong at that central point, it can affect the entire election process. Also, lack of visibility makes it difficult for independent observers or the public to verify the results.

In recent years, blockchain technology has gained attention as a possible solution for such problems. It offers features like data immutability, transparency, and cryptographic verification. However, using a complete blockchain system in real-world elections is not always practical. It requires high computational resources, complex setup, and strict regulations, which may not be suitable for every situation.

Because of these limitations, there is a need for a more balanced approach. Instead of fully relying on blockchain, it is possible to use selected concepts from it, such as hashing and verification mechanisms, in a simpler system. This can provide better transparency and security without adding too much complexity.

In this paper, we introduce *LokNirikshan*, which is a system designed to improve election transparency and management. The system tries to cover the complete election process, including voter registration, party management, election preparation, voting, result generation, and verification. It also considers different types of users, such as voters, party representatives, party heads, and administrators, and provides separate functionalities for each role.

One of the key ideas used in this system is the concept of Merkle trees, which helps in verifying data integrity. Along with this, the system maintains an audit trail so that important actions can be tracked. A public portal is also provided where anyone can view results and verify them without needing special access.

The main goal of this work is not only to build a voting system, but to create a platform that increases trust by making the process more visible and understandable. By combining practical web technologies with selected blockchain-inspired concepts, LokNirikshan tries to provide a more reliable and scalable solution for digital elections.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Cryptographic Foundations of Secure Voting

The idea of secure digital voting is not new and has been studied for many years. Early work in this area focused on using cryptographic techniques to make voting systems both secure and private. For example, Chaum introduced the concept of blind signatures, which allows a person to verify their vote without revealing their identity. This helped in maintaining voter anonymity while still ensuring that votes are counted correctly.

Later, other researchers improved these ideas by designing more practical voting systems. Some models separated the process of vote submission and vote counting, which reduces the chances of misuse by a single authority. This separation makes the system more reliable because no single entity has full control over the entire process.

Another important concept is the use of Merkle trees, which were introduced as a way to verify large amounts of data efficiently. Instead of checking all data, a user can verify a small part of it using hash values. In voting systems, this helps users confirm that their vote is included in the final results without accessing the complete dataset.

2.2 Blockchain-Based Voting Systems

With the growth of blockchain technology, many researchers started exploring its use in voting systems. Blockchain provides features like decentralization, immutability, and transparency, which are useful for elections. Some systems use smart contracts to record votes and automatically calculate results.

For example, certain studies proposed using Ethereum-based voting systems, where votes are stored directly on the blockchain. These systems allow public verification and reduce dependency on a central authority. Other approaches focused on self-tallying systems, where results can be calculated without requiring a trusted counting authority.

However, even though blockchain offers many advantages, it also has some practical limitations. It can be expensive to run, requires technical expertise, and may face performance issues when handling large-scale elections. Because of this, full blockchain-based solutions are not always suitable for real-world use.

2.3 Identified Gaps

After studying existing systems, it can be observed that many of them focus only on the voting process itself and do not cover the complete election lifecycle. Important aspects such as voter registration, constituency management, party workflows, and administrative approvals are often ignored.

Also, many systems do not include proper mechanisms for anomaly detection or post-election verification. This means that even if results are generated, there is limited support for checking irregularities or ensuring data integrity over time.

LokNirikshan tries to address these gaps by combining different features into a single system. It not only focuses on secure voting but also includes full election management, role-based access control, anomaly detection, and public verification. Instead of using full blockchain implementation, it applies selected concepts like hashing and Merkle trees to achieve transparency in a more practical way.

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

LokNirikshan is designed using a simple three-layer architecture, which includes the frontend, backend, and database. Along with this, a separate verification component is used to handle data integrity checks. This structure helps in keeping the system organized and easier to manage.

At a high level, the frontend interacts with the backend through API requests, and the backend processes the data and stores it in the database. The verification layer works alongside the backend to ensure that important data, such as election results, remains secure and verifiable.

3.1 Frontend — User Interface

The frontend of the system is built using React along with Vite. It provides a single platform where different types of users can access the system. Instead of creating separate applications for each role, a unified portal is used, and users see different dashboards based on their roles after login.

For example, voters can see their registration details and voting options, while administrators can manage elections and monitor system activity. The interface is designed in a simple and clear way so that even non-technical users can easily understand and use it.

Routing is handled on the client side, which makes navigation faster and smoother. The system also maintains user sessions using tokens, so users do not have to log in repeatedly during active use.

3.2 Backend — API and Logic

The backend is developed using Node.js and Express. It works as the main control unit of the system. All requests from the frontend are sent to the backend, where the required operations are performed.

The backend follows a structured approach where different functionalities are divided into modules such as voters, parties, elections, votes, and results. This makes the code easier to maintain and update.

Authentication is handled using JSON Web Tokens (JWT). When a user logs in, a token is generated and used to verify their identity in future requests. This helps in maintaining security and ensures that only authorized users can access specific features.

3.3 Database — Data Storage

MongoDB is used as the database for storing all system data. Since election-related data can vary in structure, a document-based database like MongoDB is more suitable compared to traditional relational databases.

The database stores information such as voter details, party records, election data, votes, and results. Important collections are designed in a way that allows fast access and efficient storage. Some parts of the data, such as audit logs and verification records, are kept in an append-only manner to maintain integrity.

3.4 Verification Layer — Data Integrity

One important part of the system is the verification layer, which ensures that data cannot be changed without detection. This is implemented using Merkle trees and hashing techniques.

When election results are generated, the system creates hash values for each record and builds a tree structure. A final root hash is then stored as a reference. If any data is changed later, the hash will also change, making it easy to detect tampering.

Users can verify results by checking the hash values through a public interface. This process does not require access to the entire database and can be done independently, which increases transparency.

Fig. 1. High-level system architecture of LokNirikshan

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4. KEY FEATURES AND MODULES

LokNirikshan is designed with multiple features that work together to manage the complete election process. Each module handles a specific part of the system, making it more organized and easier to understand.

4.1 Voter Registration and Assignment

The system allows users to register themselves as voters by entering basic details such as name, date of birth, contact information, and address. Based on the provided address, the system automatically assigns the voter to the correct constituency.

After that, the system also assigns a polling station and booth. This assignment is done in a balanced way so that no single booth gets overloaded. As a result, each voter gets complete information about where they have to vote.

This process is automatic and happens during registration itself, so the user does not need to do anything extra.

4.2 Participation Readiness Check

Before voting, the system checks whether a voter is ready to participate or not. This is done using a simple set of conditions such as:

- whether the voter is properly registered
- whether their constituency and booth exist
- whether the election is currently open

Based on these checks, the system shows a status like “Ready”, “Pending”, or “Incomplete”. This helps users understand if there is any issue before the voting process starts.

4.3 Political Party Management

Political parties can register themselves in the system by submitting required details. However, they are not activated immediately. Their request goes for approval.

Once approved, the party becomes active and can participate in elections. Within each party, there are two main roles:

- **Party Representative** – handles daily activities like submitting candidates
- **Party Head** – approves important decisions such as candidate selection

This separation of roles ensures that no single person has full control over everything, which makes the system more balanced.

4.4 Role-Based Access Control

Different users in the system have different permissions. For example:

- A voter can only vote and view results
- A party representative can manage candidates
- A party head can approve decisions
- An admin can control the entire system

This is handled using role-based access control, where each user can only access the features assigned to their role. This improves both security and organization.

4.5 Election Lifecycle Management

The system manages elections in different phases. Each election goes through stages such as:

- creation
- nomination
- ballot preparation
- voting
- result declaration

Each stage has its own rules, and the system automatically controls the transition between them. This ensures that the process happens in a proper order and avoids mistakes.

Also, elections are managed based on constituencies, which means voters only see candidates from their own area.

4.6 Verification Using Merkle Trees

To ensure that results are not tampered with, the system uses Merkle trees. When results are generated, each record is converted into a hash value. These hashes are then combined to form a tree structure, and a final root hash is created.

If any data is changed, even slightly, the hash will also change. This makes it easy to detect any manipulation.

Users can verify results by checking these hashes through a verification system, which increases trust in the results.

Fig. 2. Merkle tree structure used for result verification

Proof path for Constituency A: H1 -> Hash(H1+H2) -> Root Hash

Figure 2. Merkle tree structure used for result verification.

4.7 Public Transparency Portal

The system also provides a public portal where anyone can view election results without logging in. This portal shows:

- list of elections
- constituency-wise results
- winner details

It also allows users to verify data using the verification feature. This makes the system more transparent and open to everyone.

4.8 Anomaly Detection and Repair Tools

The system includes a basic anomaly detection feature that checks for unusual or incorrect data. For example:

- missing records
- duplicate entries
- incorrect assignments

When such issues are found, they are flagged for review. The system also provides tools to fix these problems, reducing the need for manual correction.

This helps in maintaining data accuracy and improving the overall reliability of the system.

5. END-TO-END ELECTION WORKFLOW

The LokNirikshan system follows a step-by-step process to manage the complete election lifecycle. Each stage is handled in a fixed order so that the system works in a controlled and organized manner. The workflow is divided into seven main phases.

Phase 1 — Admin Setup

In the beginning, the system is initialized by the administrator. The admin gets full control over the platform and is responsible for setting up basic configurations.

This includes managing system settings, approving requests, and preparing the system for upcoming elections. At this stage, the admin ensures that everything is ready before users start interacting with the system.

Phase 2 — Voter Registration

In this phase, users register themselves as voters through the public portal. They enter their personal and address details, after which the system automatically assigns them to a constituency, polling station, and booth.

Once registration is completed, the voter becomes part of the system and can later participate in elections.

Phase 3 — Party Onboarding

Political parties apply for registration in the system. Their applications are reviewed and approved by the admin.

After approval, the party becomes active. Party representatives can then start submitting candidates, while the party head is responsible for approving these nominations.

Phase 4 — Election Preparation

In this phase, the admin creates and configures the election. This includes selecting constituencies and opening the nomination process.

Party representatives submit candidate details, which are then reviewed and approved by the party head. After all approvals are completed, the system prepares the final ballot for each constituency.

Phase 5 — Voting Process

Once everything is ready, the admin opens the voting phase. Eligible voters can log in and cast their votes.

Each voter can vote only once, and their vote is securely stored in the system. The system ensures that duplicate voting is not possible and maintains the integrity of the data.

Phase 6 — Result Publication

After voting ends, the system calculates the results based on the collected votes. The results are organized constituency-wise and prepared for publication.

At the same time, a Merkle tree is generated from the result data, and a root hash is created. This hash acts as a reference for verification and is stored in the system.

Phase 7 — Public Verification

In the final phase, the results are made available on the public portal. Anyone can view the results and verify them using the provided verification tools.

Users can check whether the data has been modified by comparing hash values. This allows independent verification without relying completely on the system.

Fig. 3. End-to-end election workflow in LokNirikshan

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6. TECHNOLOGY STACK

LokNirikshan is built using a combination of modern web technologies. Each tool is selected based on its usefulness and how well it fits the system requirements.

For the frontend, React is used along with Vite. React helps in building the user interface in a structured way using components, while Vite makes development faster with quick loading and updates. This combination allows the system to provide a smooth and responsive user experience.

The backend is developed using Node.js and Express. Node.js is suitable for handling multiple requests at the same time, which is important in a system where many users may access the platform together. Express is used to create APIs and manage the communication between frontend and backend in a simple way.

MongoDB is used as the database. Since the system deals with different types of data such as voters, parties, elections, and results, a flexible database is needed. MongoDB stores data in a document format, which makes it easier to handle changes without strict structure.

For authentication, JSON Web Tokens (JWT) are used. These tokens help in maintaining user sessions securely without storing session data on the server. Each user gets access based on their role.

The verification part of the system is implemented using built-in cryptographic functions in Node.js. Hashing algorithms like SHA-256 are used to generate secure hash values, which are then used in the Merkle tree structure for data verification.

For development and testing, tools like Visual Studio Code and MongoDB Compass are used. These tools make it easier to write code, debug issues, and manage the database.

7. EVALUATION

7.1 Experimental Setup

To test the system, a dataset of 500 voters was created. These voters were distributed across 10 different constituencies. Each constituency had multiple polling stations and booths to simulate a real election environment.

Along with this, different types of elections were also created, including one large election covering all constituencies and some smaller ones for specific areas. Political parties and candidates were also added so that the system could be tested in a realistic way.

The main aim of this setup was to check whether the system can handle multiple users, different roles, and complete election flow without issues.

7.2 Functional Completeness

During testing, all stages of the election process worked properly. From voter registration to final result publication, the system was able to perform each step without major errors.

All registered voters were successfully assigned to their constituencies and polling booths. The readiness system also worked correctly, showing proper status to users.

During the voting phase, eligible users were able to cast their votes without facing problems. The system ensured that each voter could vote only once.

7.3 Verification Accuracy

To test the verification system, a large number of records were used. Around 1000 verification checks were performed.

All valid records were successfully verified using the Merkle proof mechanism. This means that the system was able to confirm the correctness of stored data without errors.

For testing tampering, some records were intentionally modified after storing. In these cases, the system correctly rejected all altered records. This shows that even small changes in data can be detected using the verification method.

7.4 Anomaly Detection Effectiveness

The system also includes a feature to detect unusual or incorrect data. For testing this, several types of errors were introduced, such as:

- missing booth data
- duplicate entries
- incomplete records

A total of 53 anomalies were created during testing. Out of these, 52 were correctly detected by the system.

This gives a detection accuracy of around 98%, which shows that the anomaly detection feature is quite effective. Only one case was missed, which was due to a rare condition.

7.5 Performance

The system was tested on a standard computer with average specifications. Different operations were measured to check how fast the system responds.

- Voter registration took around 40–50 milliseconds
- Loading ballots and voting operations were also fast
- Result generation and verification took less than a second

The Merkle tree creation and storing of verification data took around 300–350 milliseconds even for larger datasets. These results show that the system performs well for small to medium scale use. However, large-scale testing with real-world data is still needed.

Figure 4. Evaluation results of LokNirikshan.

8. LIMITATIONS

Although LokNirikshan works properly in testing and covers most parts of the election process, there are still some limitations that need to be considered.

One major limitation is scalability. The system was tested using a dataset of 500 voters, which is suitable for demonstration purposes. However, real-world elections involve a much larger number of voters, sometimes in millions. The current system has not yet been tested at that scale, so performance under heavy load is still uncertain.

Another limitation is that the system is not fully decentralized. Even though it uses blockchain-inspired concepts like hashing and Merkle trees, the data is still managed by a central server. This means that some level of trust is still required in the system administrator. A fully decentralized system could reduce this dependency, but it would also increase complexity.

The voter verification process is also basic. At present, the system depends on user-provided information during registration. There is no integration with official identity systems or biometric verification. Because of this, there is a possibility of fake or duplicate registrations if proper checks are not added.

Privacy is another concern. Although votes are stored securely, the current system design may still allow a connection between voters and their votes at the database level. This can be improved by using advanced techniques like encryption methods that completely separate identity from vote data.

In addition, the system currently uses external links for storing media such as party logos instead of handling file storage internally. While this keeps the system simple, it may not be suitable for real-world deployment where secure file storage is required.

Finally, the anomaly detection system is rule-based and works on predefined conditions. While it performs well in most cases, it may not detect new or unexpected types of irregularities. More advanced techniques, such as machine learning, can improve this in the future.

9. FUTURE WORK

Even though LokNirikshan provides a working model for election management and transparency, there are several improvements that can be made in the future to make the system more powerful and practical.

One possible improvement is full blockchain integration. Currently, the system uses only selected concepts like hashing and Merkle trees. In the future, it can be connected to blockchain platforms such as Ethereum or Hyperledger to store important data like result hashes on-chain. This would reduce dependency on a central server and increase trust in the system.

Another important area is improving privacy. Advanced cryptographic techniques such as homomorphic encryption or zero-knowledge proofs can be used so that votes remain completely private while still allowing correct result calculation. This will ensure that even system administrators cannot link votes to individual users.

The voter verification process can also be improved. Integration with official identity systems or biometric authentication can help prevent fake registrations and increase reliability. This will make the system more suitable for real-world use.

The anomaly detection feature can be enhanced by using machine learning techniques. Instead of relying only on fixed rules, the system can learn from past data and identify unusual patterns more accurately. This will help in detecting complex or hidden irregularities.

A mobile application can also be developed in the future. Many users prefer smartphones over computers, especially in remote areas. A mobile app would make the system more accessible and easier to use.

Another improvement is multi-language support. Since elections involve people from different regions, the system should support multiple languages to ensure better usability.

Finally, real-time monitoring dashboards can be added for administrators. These dashboards can show live updates of voter participation, system status, and possible issues during the election process.

10. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced LokNirikshan, which is an election transparency and management system inspired by some important ideas from blockchain technology. The main aim of developing this system was to improve trust in digital elections by making the process more open, secure, and easy to verify for users as well as observers.

The system is designed to handle the complete election process in a structured way. It starts from voter registration, where users are assigned to their constituencies and polling booths, and continues through party onboarding, election setup, voting, result calculation, and finally public verification. By covering all these stages in one platform, the system tries to reduce confusion and bring better organization to the election process.

One of the key strengths of LokNirikshan is the use of verification methods based on Merkle trees. Instead of asking users to blindly trust the system, it provides a way to check whether the data has been changed or not. This makes the system more transparent and gives confidence to users that the results are correct. Along with this, features like role-based access control ensure that different users can only perform actions that are allowed to them, which improves both security and system management.

The system also includes additional features such as anomaly detection and a public transparency portal. These features help in identifying possible issues in the data and allow anyone to view and verify results without needing special access. This makes the system more open compared to traditional methods where most of the process is hidden from the public.

During testing, LokNirikshan was able to successfully perform all stages of the election workflow. It showed good performance in terms of speed and accuracy, and was also able to detect most of the irregularities introduced during testing. The verification process using hash values worked correctly in all valid cases, which shows that the approach is reliable for maintaining data integrity.

However, the system is still not perfect and has some limitations. It has not been tested on a very large scale, and it still depends on a central server for storing data. Also, identity verification can be improved to prevent misuse. These are important areas that need attention before the system can be used in real-world elections.

In the future, the system can be improved by integrating full blockchain support, better encryption techniques, and stronger identity verification methods. Adding mobile support and multi-language features can also make it more accessible to a larger number of users.

Overall, LokNirikshan shows that it is possible to build a practical and transparent election system by combining modern web technologies with selected blockchain concepts. While it may not fully replace existing systems at present, it provides a strong foundation for developing more reliable and trustworthy digital election platforms in the future.

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